

Contribution by the Erasmus+ Inclusion4EU [project](#), with Informatics Europe as one of the project partners.

Inclusion4EU: Co-Design for Inclusion in Software Development Design

Inclusion4EU Consortium

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The Inclusion4EU project (www.inclusion4eu.eu) has recently come to an end, and the partnership is delighted to share its achievements, outcomes, and resources developed to support Informatics lecturers and professionals across Europe.

Inclusion4EU is an [Erasmus+](#) project involving Technological University Dublin (project lead), Télécom SudParis, Mälardalens University, Saint John of God Community Services, SAP, and Informatics Europe. The project ran for three years, starting in December 2023, bringing together higher education institutions, industry, and community organisations around a shared goal: making inclusive and universal design and co-design an integral part of how technology is taught, designed, and developed.

Why Inclusion4EU?

We began this project with a clear understanding of a paradox that defines our digital age. While the pace of technological innovation continues to accelerate, not all individuals and groups benefit equally from these advances. Some are left behind, not because technology cannot include them, but because it often isn't designed with them in mind.

People with disabilities, in particular, still lag in access to computers and digital services. Inclusive technology for people with disabilities requires a diversified and thoughtful approach that considers physical, cognitive, mental, and emotional interactions with technology, alongside ethical, privacy, and safety implications.

We firmly believed that co-design methodology could be used to make technology more accessible and equitable for all. Our strategy was to tackle the challenge from two complementary perspectives:

the classroom, where future technologists are educated, and the software development processes, supported by one of the world's largest IT multinationals, SAP.

Working Across Education and Industry

On the education side, we created a set of resources and activities aimed at supporting Informatics lecturers and upskilling staff in our partner institutions. These resources help educators apply co-design methodologies in their classrooms, fostering cohorts of graduates who are trained to listen to the lived experiences of people with disabilities and to understand their unique needs and preferences.

On the industry side, we collaborated closely with SAP to organise activities that helped staff better understand where and how inclusive design can be embedded within internal development processes. This dual approach allowed us to explore inclusive design not only as a pedagogical topic, but as a practical, organisational practice.

Research as a Starting Point

Our journey began with research. Our work began with research. In *The Dark Side of Design*, we examined how software systems and organisational practices can unintentionally become exclusionary, while *The Bright Side of Design* highlighted the benefits of inclusive design and showcased examples of good practice, demonstrating its value beyond ethical or legal compliance.

To understand how inclusive design is taught in Informatics programmes across Europe, we conducted a survey in early 2024 involving 35

universities from 22 countries. The results were revealing. While awareness of inclusive design is growing, its implementation remains uneven: half of the institutions surveyed had not integrated it into their curricula, citing barriers such as curriculum overload and lack of expertise. Even where it is taught, students often receive fewer than five hours of instruction per semester.

These findings are collected in three dedicated research reports, all available for consultation and download in the [research section of our website](#).

From Research to Action: Co-Design at the Core

Having identified the gap, our response was clear: make universal design and co-design easier to

understand, teach, and apply in practice. To achieve this, we developed a set of tools and resources grounded in co-design methodologies.

Through a series of co-design sessions with underrepresented groups, educators, students, and industry practitioners, we created resources that enable organisations and lecturers to meaningfully embed co-design in their work. Sessions involved older adults, Computer Science students and lecturers, academic staff, and industry professionals from SAP.

While each session brought different perspectives, they all reinforced the same message: inclusive design is most effective when people are genuinely involved in the process, not simply consulted.

One of Inclusion4EU's Co-Design Sessions.

Resources and the Inclusion4EU Charter

All project resources are available for consultation and download in the [resources section of our website](#). At the heart of these outputs is the Inclusion4EU Charter, the core resource developed through our investigation.

The Charter is a practical tool designed to support the planning and facilitation of co-design sessions. It functions as a comprehensive environment to collect outputs across all stages of co-design, from discovery and ideation to prototyping and evaluation.

A frame from the Inclusion4EU Charter.

Training and Capacity Building

We also delivered two training programmes to upskill academic staff in running co-design sessions. Asynchronous materials from this training will soon be available on the website. In addition, we ran a dedicated training programme for training professionals, involving co-designers from TU Dublin and Saint John of God Community Services.

Feedback from participants was overwhelmingly positive. One participant noted, “The Charter provided a very helpful map of what we were to

work on, when to work on which piece, and in which order - it gave us a clear target.” Another reflected, “I was surprised by how much more co-design can bring to both designers and co-designers. Even though I work with Universal Design, this is something special.” Perhaps most tellingly, one participant shared, “I always thought of design as design-for, not design-with, and this changed my view.”

That shift in perspective is, in many ways, the project’s greatest success.

A photo from the 2025 training course.

Looking Ahead

Many people contributed to the success of Inclusion4EU, but above all, it was the sustained participation of co-designers throughout all stages of the project that made it truly inclusive and impactful. For this, we extend our deepest thanks to all co-designers involved.

The partnership plans to continue its work by implementing at least one co-design training session per year, so we encourage you to keep an eye on the website for upcoming events. More

broadly, we hope you will use the Inclusion4EU website to stay informed, download resources, and—if you wish—upload your own.

You can contact us at any time or share your thoughts through our [LinkedIn page](#). We hope our work will inspire you to bring co-design methodologies into your classes, institutions, organisations, and perhaps even into how you see technology in everyday life. After all, inclusion works best when everyone has a seat at the table and a say in how the chairs are designed.

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